

Water management

Yield and water use efficiency of newly developed rice mutants under different water management practices

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We tested the effects of water management on newly developed rice mutants BINA 4-39-15-13 and BINA 4-5-17-19. Practices tested were continuous ponding (5 ± 2 cm water) and application of 5 cm water at 3, 5, and 7 d after disappearance of ponded water (DAP).

At final land preparation, each plot was fertilized uniformly with a basal dose of 60 kg N/ha as urea, 26.4 kg P/ha as triple superphosphate, 33.2 kg K/ha as muriate of potash, 10 kg S/ha as gypsum, and 4 kg Zn/ha as zinc oxide. Another 20 kg N/ha (as urea) was topdressed, half at active vegetative phase and half at flowering.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design. Forty-five-d-old seedlings were planted in a sandy loam soil at the BINA farm the first week of Feb 1992. Irrigation was applied in main plot treatments (5- x 6-m plots) and in rice mutant subplot treatments (5- x 3-m plots). We applied 3-5 cm water to all treatment plots for the first 2 wk to allow for crop establishment and then irrigation treatments were followed. BINA 4-39-15-13 was harvested the third week of May, and BINA 4-5-17-19 was harvested 15 d later.

Continuous ponding required about 214% more water for irrigation than the other treatments, but produced only 13, 15, and 15% more grain than when 5 cm water was applied at 3, 5, and 7 DAP, respectively (see table).

BINA 4-5-17-19 produced significantly more grain (8.1 t/ha), straw, and tillers/plant, than BINA 4-39-15-13 (7.5 t/ha). The 7 DAP treatment required the least water and had the highest water use efficiency (see table) and is recommended for areas where water is costly. Yield, however, was 1.1 t/ha less than under continuous ponding. ■

Number of irrigations, water requirement, and water use efficiency of rice mutants under different water management practices. BINA Farm, Mymensingh, Bangladesh, 1992 dry season.

Treatment	Irrigation (no.)	Amount of irrigation water ^a	Water requirement (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency (kg/ha per cm)
Continuous ponding (5 ± 2 cm water)	Almost every other day	220	273.95	8.6	7.0	36.10
Application of water 3 DAP ^b	7	70	87.95	7.7	6.4	86.98
Application of water 5 DAP	7	70	87.95	7.5	6.2	85.04
Application of water 7 DAP	5	60	77.95	7.5	6.9	95.95

^aIncludes 30 cm of water for crop establishment. Amount of rainfall is 17.95 cm. ^bDAP = d after disappearance of ponded water.

Farming systems

Identification of recommendation domains for technology generation and transfer in rice culture

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We conducted a study to identify the recommendation domains for the technology generation and transfer processes in the coastal rice-growing agroecological zone of Matara district, Sri Lanka. Exploratory studies were carried out during 1990-91 wet season and 1991 dry season to understand prevailing production conditions. A random sample

of 291 farmers were surveyed using a pretested questionnaire to identify production problems.

Saline soil, acidic soil, water deficit, and excess water were identified as problems. All vary according to elevation.

The area was classified into three domains: upper (>1 msl), intermediate (1-0 msl), and lower (>0 msl). An index (based on a scoring procedure) was constructed to estimate intensity of the problem. Farmers were located on this scale. Scores were divided into four categories. Actual score for a particular problem was presented as a percentage and assigned an intensity category (see table).

Study locations can be classified into three recommendation domains on the

Three recommendation domains based on production conditions. Matara district, Sri Lanka.

Recommendation domain	Farmers (no.)	Sample size (no.)	Intensity of problems (%)			
			Soil acidification	Soil salinization	Water deficit	Excess water
Upper	2562	126	76-100 (very high)	na	76-100 (very high)	na
Intermediate	1771	89	26-50 (moderate)	na	51-75 (high)	na
Lower	1504	76	0-25 (low)	51-75 (high)	na	51-75 (high)

^ana = not applicable.